

Green synthesis of silver Nanoparticle using *Carica Papaya* and study there Biochemical Application

¹Ms.Pallavi R.Bhagat, ²Ms. Shubhangi Sahebsingh Rajput

³Ms. Shruti Prashant Chavan

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7296295>

Published Date: 06-November-2022

Abstract: The nanoparticle offer several advantages over other conventional drug delivery systems. Nanoparticles have gained importance in technological advancements due to their modifiable physical, chemical and biological properties with improved performance over their bulk foils. Nanoparticles can simply move in the body due to their small size and reach very complex organs through divers routes. The high stability, controlled drug release makes nanoparticles the most suitable drug delivery system. The study of different methods of synthesis of nanoparticles is essential to obtain desired nanoparticle with specific sizes and shapes. They are suitable candidates for various marketable and local application, which include imaging, catalysis medical application and environmental application.

Keywords: Nanoparticle, bulk foil, divers routes.

1. INTRODUCTION

It may appear that Nanotechnology is of recent origin. Actually, it dates back several thousands of years like use of gold nanoparticles in tinting of glass used to make goblets and also to cure certain diseases. This is because nanoparticle have altered properties than their base metallic elements.(15) In 1875 Faraday was the first person to recognize metallic nanoparticles as unique nanostructures with distinctive properties. Various synthesis methods are adopted to for the preparation of metallic distinctive properties. Various synthesis methods are adopted to for the preparation of metallic nanoparticles. These are either top down or bottom up approach. However, each of these approaches has certain advantages and limitations. Both these methods are physico-chemical in nature.(2)

Synthesis approaches:

1. Top-down approach

The top-down approach uses initial macroscopic structures. The methods begin with larger particles which are reduced to nanoparticles after a sequence of operations performed over them. Main shortcoming of these methods are that they involve large installation and huge capital is required for set up. The methods are quite expensive and not suitable for large-scale production. The method is suitable for laboratory experimentation. The approach is based upon the grinding of materials. These methods are not suitable for soft sample.(16,10)

Methods in Top-down approach:

1. Physical vapour deposition.
2. Chemical vapour deposition.
3. Ion implantation.

4. Electron beam lithography.

5. X-ray lithography.

2. Bottom-up approach

Bottom-up approaches of production of nanomaterials comprise the miniaturization of materials constituents to the atomic level with the additional procedure leading to the development of nanostructures. Throughout the further progression, the physical forces working at nanoscale combined simple units into larger stable structures. The methodology is principally based on the principle of molecular recognition. Self-assembly means growing more and more things about one's kind from themselves. Many of these techniques are still under development nor are just beginning to be used for the commercial production of nanoparticles.(8,4)

Methods in a bottom-up approach:

1. Sol-gel synthesis

2. Colloidal precipitation

3. Hydrothermal synthesis 4. Organometallic chemical route

5. Electrodeposition.

Methods of synthesis of nanoparticles

1. Physical methods

a) Mechanical method

b) Pulse laser ablation

c) Pulsed wire discharge method

d) Chemical vapor Deposition

e) Laser pyrolysis

f) Ionized cluster beam Deposition

2. Chemical methods

a) Sol-gel method

b) Sonochemical synthesis

c) Co-precipitation method

d) Inert gas condensation method

e) Hydrothermal synthesis

3. Biological methods

a) Synthesis using microorganisms

b) Synthesis using plant extracts

c) Synthesis using algae

Carica papaya

Papaya is a powerhouse of nutrients and is available throughout the year. It is a rich source of three powerful antioxidant vitamin C, vitamin A and vitamin E. the mineral, magnesium and potassium; the B vitamin pantothenic acid and folate and fiber. In addition to all this, it contains a digestive enzyme-papain that effectively treats cause of trauma, allergies and sports injuries. All the nutrients of papaya as a whole improve cardiovascular system, protect against heart diseases, heart attacks,

strokes and prevent colon cancer. The fruit is an excellent source of beta carotene that prevents damage caused by free radicals that may cause some forms of cancer. It is reported that it helps in the prevention of diabetic heart disease. Papaya lowers high cholesterol levels as it is a good source of fiber. (9)

Papaya effectively treats and improve all types of digestive and abdominal disorders. It is a medicine for dyspepsia, hyperacidity, dysentery and constipation. Papaya helps in the digestion of proteins as it is a rich source of proteolytic enzymes. Even papain-a digestive enzyme found in papaya is extracted, dried as a powder and used as an aid in digestion. Ripe fruit consumed regularly helps in habitual constipation. It is also reported that papaya prevents premature aging. It may be that it works because a poor digestion does not provide nutrients to our body. The fruit is regarded as a remedy for abdominal disorders, the skin of works as a best medicine for wounds. Even you can use the pulp left after extracting the juice from papaya as poultice on the wounds. The enzymes papain and chymopapain and antioxidant nutrients found in papaya have been found helpful in lowering inflammation and healing burns. That is why people with diseases that are worsened by inflammation, find relief as the severity of the condition reduces after taking all these nutrients.(1)

Biological sources

- Botanical name: Carica papaya
- Family name: caricaceae
- Common name: Papaya, paw paw, kates, papaw • Part used: leaves, fruits, bark.

Cosmetic benefits of papaya

Rubbing the white pulp of papaya improves pimples as well as wrinkles. Papaya works as a good bleaching agent. It is an important ingredient in bath soaps, astringents, detergent bars and hand washes. Home recipe for papaya skin lighter experts suggest that papaya can help in removing dead worn-out skin cells and replace it with healthy new cells, thereby lightening the color of our skin. For this, one can prepare a paste of raw papaya and apply it on the skin once for few days.(13)

2. METHODS

Collection and preparation of extract:

Fresh leaves of Carica papaya (pawpaw), collected separately from a local area. The plant leaves were thoroughly washed with tap water to remove dust particles and other unwanted materials accumulated on the leaves. The dust free leaves were pulverized and kept to dry under shade in the Pharmaceutics laboratory for 24 h. The dried leaves were then powdered by using an electric blender.

Extraction Procedure:

Fresh leaves of Carica papaya (pawpaw), collected separately from a local area. The plant leaves were thoroughly washed with tap water to remove dust particles and other unwanted materials accumulated on the leaves. Were diced into fine pieces and transferred into sterile distilled water and heated at 60°C for 5-10min and incubated in a sand bath for 30 min to facilitate aqueous extract. The extract was filtered using filter paper and the filtrate extract was stored at 4°C for further analysis.

Synthesis of silver nanoparticles:

10 mL of 1% silver nitrate (AgNO_3) was prepared by dissolving 0.1 g of silver nitrate (AgNO_3) in 10ml of water followed by incorporation of 5 ml of the extract in drops under constant stirring using a magnetic stirrer assembly for 5 min, to obtain $[\text{Ag}]^+$ dispersion. 25 mL aliquot of a freshly prepared aqueous extract of Carica papaya leaves (reducing agent) was added to the resultant mixture and maintained at 40°C temperature for 24 h. The resultant suspension of Silver nanoparticle was lyophilized (using Virtis 2KBTXL-75 Benchtop SLC Freeze Dryer) and subject to further analysis.

Characterisation of Silver Nano-Composites (UV-VIS Spectroscopy):

UV-Vis spectral analysis using a double beam spectrophotometer with the samples dispersed in distilled water and kept in a quartz cuvette with a path length of 10 mm. The photoluminescence emission spectra from the samples (dispersed in distilled water) were recorded by a spectrofluorometer (LS 55, Perkin Elmer) at room temperature using a four side polished quartz cuvette with a path length of 10 mm.

Antioxidant activity:

The antioxidant activity of *C. papaya* extract was determined by the method of with slight modification using the stable DPPH scavenging. Briefly, samples extract with various concentrations was prepared 30, 60, 90, 120, and 150 µg/mL. Each sample was mixed with 1.0 mL of 0.4 mM DPPH solution. All the solutions were prepared with methanol to 5.0 mL. Experiment is done in triplicate. The test sample is incubated for 30 min at room temperature and the absorbance is measured at 517 nm. Ascorbic acid was used as a standard at concentration of 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 µg/mL and DPPH in methanol was used as a control. The difference in absorbance between the test and the control was calculated and expressed as % scavenging of DPPH radical (% inhibitions). Then, % inhibitions were plotted against respective concentration used and from the graph IC50 calculated.

Purification and Identification:

Purification is conducted using TLC preparative. The ethanol extract is analyzed by TLC method using silica gel GF254 with three solvents mixture: n-hexane-ethyl acetate (9:1, 4:1), ethyl acetate-methanol (3:7, 4:6), and chloroform-methanol (7:3, 6:4). The spots were visually identified under 254 nm and 366 nm UV lamp.

Antimicrobial Diffusion Method:

The antimicrobial activity of silver nanoparticles is carried out against both Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria. The synthesized silver nanoparticles exhibit good antibacterial activity against both Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis of silver nanoparticles from carica papaya leaves synthesized by adding AgNO₃ solution in leaf extraction in overnight colour change was observed brown colour are formed in antimicrobial activity. *S.aureus* and *E.coli* show antimicrobial activity against silver nanoparticles solution. Phytochemical screening of leaves extraction contains phenols, tanins, steroids, coumarins, terpenoid, flavonoids. The UV absorption of spectrophotometric analysis

REFERENCES

- [1] Akhtar, Mohd Sayeed & Panwar, Jitendra & Yun, Yeoung-Sang. (2013). Biogenic synthesis of metallic nanoparticles by plant extracts. *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering*, 1: *international journal of science and research* 591-602.
- [2] Biswas, A, Bayer, I. S, Biris, A. S, Wang. T, Dervishi. E, & Faupel. F. (2012). Advances in top-down and bottom-up surface nanofabrication: techniques, applications & future prospects. *Advances in colloid and interface science*, 170(1-2): 2-27.
- [3] Carlin. E, Contar. J, & Silva-Filho. D.P. (1986). Pharmacology of Lemon Grass & Effect of teas Prepared from leaves on laboratory animals. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 17(1): 37-64.
- [4] Doyle, M.E., Glass, K.A., (2010) Sodium reduction and its effect on food safety, food quality, and human health. *Compr Rev Food Sci Food Saf*; 9:44-56.
- [5] Gour, A, & Jain. N. K, (2019). Advances in green synthesis of nanoparticles. *Artificial cells, Nanomedicine, and biotechnology*, 47(1): 844-851.
- [6] Hou, T.H., Su C.H., Liu, W.L. Parameters optimization of a nanoparticle wet milling process using the Taguchi method, response surface method and genetic algorithm. *Powder Technol*; 173:153-62.
- [7] Khan, I. & Saeed, K. & Khan, I. (2017). Nanoparticles: Properties, Applications and Toxicities. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 10:1016.
- [8] Koch, C.C. (1997) Synthesis of nanostructured materials by mechanical milling: problems and opportunities. *Nanostructured Materials*; 9:13-22.
- [9] Krishnappa, K., Pandiyan, J., Paramanandham, J., Elumalai, K., (2018). Antibacterial and mosquitocidal potentials of selected Indian medicinal plants extracts and synthesized silver nanoparticles. *Int J Zool Studies*; 3:15-5.

- [10] Mittal, A. K., Chisti, Y., & Banerjee, U. C. (2013). Synthesis of metallic nanoparticles using plant extracts. *Biotechnology advances*,31(2):346–356.
- [11] Muñoz, J.E., Cervantes, J., Esparza, R., Rosas, G.,(2007). Iron nanoparticles produced by high-energy ball milling. *J Nanopart Res* ;9:945-50.
- [12] N. Sap-Lam, C. Homklinchan, R. Larpudomlert, W. Warisnoicharoen, A. Sereemaspun, and S. T. Dubas (2010). UV irradiation induced silver nanoparticles as mosquito larvicides. *Journal of Applied Sciences*,10(23): 3132–3136.
- [13] Rangarajan, M., Vasanthakumari, R., Vikram, S.,(2014).Superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles from coprecipitation: composition, size, and magnetization. *Nanosci Nanotechnol*:14:1-9.
- [14] S. Garima, B. Riju, K. Kunal, R. S. Ashish, and P. S. Rajendra (2011). Biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles using *Ocimum sanctum* (Tulsi) leaf extract and screening its antimicrobial activity. *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*,13(7): 2981–2988.
- [15] S. L. Lui, V. K. M. Poon, I. Lung, and A. Burd. (2006) Antimicrobial activities of silver dressings’: an in vitro comparison. *Journal of Medical Microbiology*,55(1):59–63.
- [16] Singh, P, Kim, Y. J, Zhang, D, & Yang. D. C (2016). Biological synthesis of nanoparticles from plants and microorganisms.,*Trends in biotechnology*,34(7):588–599.
- [17] Siwach, O.P., Sen P., (2008).Synthesis and study of fluorescence properties of Cu nanoparticles. *J Nanoparticle Res* ;10:107-14.